

Development of Creativity in Preschool Children Based on the Introduction of an Artistic Work

Abdirafimova Muxlisa Abduxoliq qizi

Pedagogical Institute, 1st year master's student, pre-school education

Article information:

Manuscript received: 04 Sep 2024; **Accepted:** 04 Oct 2024; **Published:** 11 Nov 2024

Abstract: In this article, the impact of works of art on preschoolers and how they form feelings in children, as well as how the process of introducing works of art is carried out and what methods are effective in giving understanding to different age groups and strengthening the read work methods are described in detail.

Keywords: Fiction, methodical activity, expressive presentation, creativity, staging, different age groups, folklore, perception, mnemonics, repeated reading, speech, genres, content of the work.

INTRODUCTION

It is known from the past that the oral creation of the people was passed from mouth to mouth. Before putting their children to sleep, our grandmothers and mothers used to tell fairy tales, fairy tales, stories, epics, short stories and poetic passages. Even now, activities are carried out on the basis of introducing artistic works to children in pre-school education organizations. The question arises as to why this is necessary for children and what effect it has.

Acquaintance of children with fiction in the preschool education organization primarily develops children's speech, as well as a trip to the world of fairy tales develops children's imagination, their fantasy. In fairy tales, protecting innocent people and punishing bad people encourages children to be just. Children begin to compare the information they have learned from the works with real life and begin to imitate positive characters. In addition, the role of fiction literature in the development of aesthetic and moral education of children is huge. Children live in fairy tales and get into the emotions of fairy tale characters, that is, when the characters laugh, they smile, when they are sad, they are sad, and when they are happy, they are happy. Literary literature helps preschool children to develop humanitarian feelings, sympathy, kindness, friendship, caring for children, parents and older members of the family.

The form, features, rhyme, rhythm and other aspects of the work of art should be suitable for children's age characteristics. Methodological duties of a teacher include:

1. Forming and noticing children's interest in books;
2. Formation of the ability to understand pictorial expressions and verbal description;
3. To isolate the individual actions of the characters and prepare them to use them in question-and-answer.

One of the methods used in the pre-school educational organization to introduce children to fiction is the staging method. Children are given various small episodes and summarized in the form of a scene. Through this method, children's sensory skills, creativity, accessibility, agility and skills of working together with other children are formed.

Mnemonic approaches are used for easy memorization of poems for children. In mnemonics, attention is paid to defining the word at the beginning of the line of the poem with conditional expressions. Then the children remember the word at the beginning of the line by looking at the signs and recite it by heart. This is repeated several times, and you will see that the children will memorize the poem without difficulty.

Another way to introduce children to literature is listening and understanding. If the teacher is effective, expressive and reads the book in the role, it will give a very good result in the listening and understanding of the children. Analyzing the listened work, understanding its meaning, describing it in one's own words are the stages of working with an artistic work. There is also a way to display a work of art in a presentational way. The combination of both methods during the experimental test work is called the "Expressive presentation" method. In this, the roles in the expressive read-out work are distributed using the selection of closed pictures. Then, the tasks for the performance of the roles are explained to each child.

It is necessary to teach children to distinguish genres of literary works from the small group. Educators should tell children the genre of the work of art. It is appropriate to tell stories to children of preschool age without reading them from a book. In this, the skills of hearing and understanding speech are formed.

In the middle group, the perception of the artistic work plays an important role. Children begin to clearly express their attitude towards the characters in the play. The teacher addresses the children with various questions. Children express their opinions. Correct analysis of a work of art increases the value of artistic speech, prepares children for independent storytelling.

Children of a large group have the ability to deeply understand some features of the content of artistic works, the expressiveness of their content. Pupils of this group can easily distinguish one genre of work from another. After the work is read or narrated, the questions asked to the children should help to determine the content of the work, to understand it, and to teach them to evaluate the behavior of the characters.

The goal of the teacher of the preparatory group for the school from the first reading of the work is to convey the work to the listeners as a work of art. They analyze more deeply and focus on the means of artistic expression.

There are several methodical ways to remember the read work: re-reading, telling a story, staging, etc.

Repeat reading. The story or small work read to children is re-read 2 or 3 times. This method helps to keep it in the memory for a long time.

Staging a work of art. This method is also one of the effective methods. In addition to the children's acting and playing, this work will be imprinted in their memory for a long time.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is worth saying that creativity develops in preschool children based on the introduction of an artistic work. Educators should read more works of art to children of preschool age in a fluent, understandable and clear manner. At this point, it is appropriate to ask the children to retell the story. In addition, the ability of children to remember and the ability to preserve books and treat them with care is also formed.

REFERENCES:

1. "State requirements for children of primary and preschool age" Decision No. 802 dated 22.12.2020 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan Appendix 1
2. "The first step" Davkat educational program - T.2022
3. State standard "On preschool education and upbringing".-T.2020
4. M.R. Kadirova, F.R. Kadirova "Theory and methodology of children's speech development" Tashkent 2006 year 34 p.
5. F. Kadirova, Sh. Toshpolatova, M. Azamova "Pedagogy before school" - T "Spirituality". 2019
6. N.M. Qayumova "Pedagogy before school". "Thoughts" T:2013
7. R. Zhorakulov "Cultivation of children's speech" Samarkand, 1994 p. 89
8. Q. Shodiyeva "Teaching preschool children to correct pronunciation" Tashkent, 1995 year 174 p.